

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

CALIBRATOR OF ALMONDS WITH ELECTROMAGNETIC VIBRATION DRIVE OF RECIPROCATING MOTION

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to discuss the development of almond production and export opportunities of Georgia; The energy-saving almond calibration method - calibration unit equipped with the direct current magnetic electromagnetic reciprocating vibration motor, with the ability to change the number of fractions and adjust the productivity; Determined of the vibrocalibration process of almonds the optimal technological parameters of the process: the speed of movement of the almond on the screen surface, which in turn depends on the coefficient of friction, the angle of inclination of the vibroscreen towards the horizon, the frequency, amplitude and direction of oscillation.

Keywords: almond, calibration, electromagnetic, screen, vibrating motor.

Introduction

World consumption of almonds is growing every year, which in turn provides for an increase in production [1]. Almond has a fairly wide and versatile use. Its processing makes it possible to obtain a wide range of

products such as almond oil, flour, milk, which are actively used in the confectionery industry, medicine and perfumery. Fig. 1 shows a diagram of world almond (Kernel Basis) production from 2010/11 to 2020/21 [2].

Fig. 1: World almond (Kernel Basis) production (Metric Tons) from 2010/11 to 2020/21

From the diagram shown in Fig. 2 it can be seen, that the global almond (kernel basis) crop totaled over 1,684,395 MT (Metric Tons) in 2020/21, the first largest production in the last 10 years. USA's crop accounted 79% of the world total, and was estimated at

1,333,562 MT. Australia and Spain came in second with 7% of the market share, respectively. Australia has more than doubled its almond production in the last ten years, surpassing the 100,000 MT milestone. Spain also hit the 100,000 MT benchmark in 2020/21[2].

Fig. 2: World almond production 2020/21 (Kernel Basis, MT)

Figure 3 shows a diagram of world almond (Kernel equivalent - Shelled + in-shell converted to kernel basis based on 35% shell) exports in 2009-2019 years [2].

Fig. 3: World almond (Kernel equivalent) exports from 2009 to 2019 (MT)

Spain's shelled almond shipments (102,895 MT) were mainly destined for other European Union countries (85%) –headed by Germany, Italy and France. Asia (50%), mostly China, and the European Union (31%), led by Germany, were Australia's top shelled

almond destinations (42,704 MT). Australia also exported a significant quantity of in-shell almonds (48,068 MT), mostly to China (71%) followed by India (24%) [2].

Fig. 4: World almond (Kernel equivalent) exports in 2019 (MT)

Almond production was practically non-existent in Georgia. Only non-commercial varieties were common, also on a very small scale and endemic Georgian almond, which is a shrub and reaches a height of 1.5 m. In 2015, the commercial varieties of this cultivar and the development of industrial almond orchards have been actively started in Georgia. The state program „Plant the Future“ played a big role in the widespread distribution and development of commercial almond orchards, within which most of the almond orchards were planted and the process is still active [3].

According to today's data, up to 4500 ha of almond orchards have been cultivated in Georgia. However, given that this trend is growing, it is expected that this figure will increase dramatically in the coming years. 2021 is the first year a significant amount of almonds are produced in the country. The first orchards, which

were planted in 2015, went into full growth this year, and farmers received a full harvest from these orchards this year. Consequently, almond production will increase more and more every year. Unlike walnuts and hazelnuts, there were no accurate statistics on almond production in Georgia. According to forecasts by the Almond and Walnut Producers Association (Association), which relies on the country's registered almond growers bases, Georgia will harvest about 1,500 MT of almonds this year, much of which will be absorbed by the local market. From next year, if the local industry is ready to meet the season, the export of Georgian almonds will definitely start. The association predicts what the almond crop will look like in the coming years (Fig. 5) [4].

Fig. 5: Almond (Shelled) harvest forecast in Georgia in 2021-27 (MT)

This calculation is based only on data from gardens planted before 2020. According to the association, Kakheti is the leader among the regions in terms of cultivated almond areas, in particular Sagarejo municipality, where almost half of the whole industry is located. In general, almonds are grown in only three regions of Georgia: Kakheti, Kvemo Kartli and Shida Kartli.

The almond industry is very new in Georgia and there is no relevant experience. It is necessary to share international experience in order to develop the industry as quickly and with less mistakes as possible. It is possible that in 10 years Georgia will be in the top ten almond producing countries. We note here that this is possible if the area of almond orchards increases and the local almond industry rapidly absorbs international experience, at the same time, it is important to create and develop modern almond processing plants [4].

Technological advances in the agricultural machinery sector play a vital role in meeting the needs of the population. The development trend of vibration calibrators has arisen due to a number of development

needs such as cost, quality, size, competition, productivity, etc. [5,6]. Vibration technologies in almond processing schemes are known [7].

Objective

The aim of the work is to study a almond calibrator equipped with a reciprocating electromagnetic vibration motor, analyze the vibrocalibration process of almonds and determine the optimal technological parameters of the process.

Theory

Analysis of the calibration process and study of the modern constructions showed that the best calibration of the almonds can be achieved by using of reciprocal motion. Therefore, we have developed a almonds calibration vibrating plant (Fig. 6), which is used as a drive, as well as our patented reciprocal motion electromagnetic vibrating motors (Fig. 6, # 1) with direct current magnetic biasing [8,9,10], where the oscillation amplitude of the operating elements can be adjusted by changing of the bias direct current.

Fig. 6: Calibrator of almonds with electromagnetic vibration drive of reciprocating motion. 1 - vibration motor; 2 - frame; 3 – hanging elastic system; 4 - vibrating tray; 5 - hopper; 6 - screens with openings of different sizes.

The almonds from the hopper (Fig. 6, # 5) are supplied to the vibrating tray (Fig. 6, # 4), in which several screens (Fig. 6, # 6) are placed one above the other, with openings of different sizes (the number of screens depends on how many fractions we want to calibrate the almonds). The almonds will be divided into several fractions, of which I will be small-sized almonds and impurities, which are necessarily found in raw materials for the first time, large II fractions, and so on. The number of fractions can be changed if necessary.

Under the influence of vibration there are: transportation, self-sorting and crushing of almonds. During the calibration process, the almonds move on the screen in the direction of the exit and are divided into two fractions: a) which move in the screen openings, b) which can not pass and move on the screen surface towards the exit.

Consider the process of moving a almond with a mass m , kg along surface $ABCD$ of one of the screens of the calibrator, forming an angle α with the horizon (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7: Scheme of the action of forces on a almond moving on the surface of a vibroscreen pronated at an angle α to the horizon

In the XOY coordinate system, a almond that fails to pass through the screen opening will have the following equilibrium condition [11,12]

$$\begin{cases} m\ddot{x} = F_f - mg \sin \alpha + F_i \cos \beta = 0 \\ m\ddot{y} = N - mg \cos \alpha + F_i \sin \beta = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

It is affected by the gravity force $P = mg$, N ; g - acceleration due to gravity, m/s^2 ; N - normal reaction, N ; $F_f = Nf_s$ - friction force, N ; f_s - coefficient of sliding friction and $F_i = mx_m \omega^2 \sin \omega t$, N - force of inertia; x_m is amplitude of oscillation of the vibroscreen, m , ω - angular frequency of oscillation, s^{-1} . t - time, s ; and β - angle of direction of oscillations towards the surface of $ABCD$ screen, arcdegree.

In order for the almond to move from x_0 to point x_1 on the screen surface (Fig. 7), the condition $m\ddot{x} > 0$ or $F_i \cos \beta > mg \sin \alpha - F_f$, from which

$$x_m \omega^2 \sin \omega t \cos \beta > g \sin \alpha - \frac{N}{m} f_s. \quad (2)$$

Depending on the operating modes, the almonds can move:

a) Disconnected from the screen surface when $N < 0$. Accordingly, the reset parameter depends on the amplitude of the transverse force of the inertial force, the amplitude of the transverse force of the force of gravity.

$$w_0^* = \frac{x_m \omega^2 \sin \beta}{g \cos \alpha} > 1$$

b) Without breaking-off the almond from the surface, $N > 0$, that is when $w_0^* < 1$.

Our studies have shown that, taking into account the physical and mechanical properties of almonds, calibration using a reciprocating vibration motor is more effective when almonds moving without break away from the sieve surface, for which it is necessary to justify the following parameters and operating modes of

the vibration calibrator: frequency ω and direction angle β of oscillations; vibration amplitude x_m ; shape and dimensions of the sieve openings. In this case, $Y = 0$ and the friction force

$$F_f = \begin{cases} -f_s N, \dot{x} < 0 \\ f_s N, \dot{x} > 0 \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

but when the almond that cannot pass through the screen to the surface is in a stationary position ($X = 0$, $Y = 0$), then the dry friction force can be calculated from (1) $F_{df} = -mgs \sin \alpha + F_i \cos \beta$, however, this state is maintained until the inequality $-f_s N < F_{df} < f_s N$ is completed, where f_s is the coefficient of static friction; usually $f_s \geq f_s$.

For effective calibration of the almonds, taking into account the shape of the vibroscreen openings selected by us, it is advisable to use the mode when the almond slides in one direction from point x_0 to point x_1 (Fig. 7).

In the XOY coordinate system, the almond that moves through the opening (Fig. 8) will have the following equation of motion:

$$\begin{cases} m\ddot{x} = -F_i \cos \beta \\ m\ddot{y} = -mg + F_i \sin \beta \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

from which, after the corresponding transformations, we obtain the speed of movement of the almond

$$v_a = \sqrt{(x_m \cos \omega t \cos \beta)^2 + (-gt - x_m \omega \cos \omega t \sin \beta)^2}, \quad (5)$$

which depends on the amplitude, the frequency and the angle of direction of the oscillations. These values, as well as the distance to the next screen surface on which the almonds to be driven into the upper screen should fall, should be selected so that jumps are minimized.

Fig. 8: Scheme of action of forces on a almond moving in the opening of the vibroscreen pronated at an angle α to the horizon

It should be noted that the presented vibrating unit is easily adaptable and can be used directly from the hopper as a dispenser for dosed delivery for almond cracking machine.

Results

The results of the obtained theoretical and experimental studies show, that if the width of vibrating

chute of the calibrator is $b = 0.6\text{m}$, height $h = 0.15\text{m}$, length $l = 1.5\text{m}$ and amplitude of oscillations $X_m = 0 \dots 0,0015\text{m}$ with oscillation frequency $\omega = 314\text{ sec}^{-1}$, the almonds can be calibrated almond disconnecting from the screen surface at the values of β and α , given in the Table 1.

Table 1

Value limits of vibration angle β and chute angle α in vibrating calibrator for calibration of almonds without disconnecting from the screen surface for specific values of X_m and ω

#	X_m, m	ω, sec^{-1}	β^0	α^0	w_0^*
1	0,0005	314	$0^\circ \leq \beta \leq 11^\circ$	$0^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 15^\circ$	$0 \leq w_0^* \leq 0,992$
2	0,0010	314	$0^\circ \leq \beta \leq 5^\circ$	$0^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 28^\circ$	$0 \leq w_0^* \leq 0,991$
3	0.0015	314	$0^\circ \leq \beta \leq 3^\circ$	$0^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 37^\circ$	$0 \leq w_0^* \leq 0,987$

Conclusion

For calibration of almond It is advisable to use a device equipped with a reciprocating electromagnetic vibration motor ue to its design simplicity and high reliability of operation and energy saving.

Determined of the vibrocalibration process of almonds the optimal technological parameters of the process: the speed of movement of the almond on the screen surface, which in turn depends on the coefficient of friction, the angle of inclination of the vibroscreen towards the horizon, the frequency, amplitude and direction of oscillation. Besides the productivity and amplitude of oscillation can be adjusted by changing of the bias direct current.

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